

ISic3549

I.Sicily inscription 3549

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

dedication

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Drepanum

Place of origin (modern)

Trapani

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Lost, Museo Pepoli (Trapani) ms. 33 and 221

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI337213

1. Ἀρχηγέτ[η]ι εὐχὴ Ἡρακλεῖ Θαλλοφόρῳ
2. ἱερῶ εὐαγσεστάτῳ ²⁶εὐαγεστάτῳ²⁶ [Λ](οὔκιος) Κορνήλιος Λ (ουκίου)
3. Κορνηλίου υἱὸς [Π]α[λ](ατίνα) ²ΓΑΝ, cory² Τερεντιανὸς
4. καὶ Λήμνιος ἀπελεύθ[ε]ρος ἐποίησαν
5. Π Π ²⁷ρ(ropria) ρ(ecunia) or ρ(ecunia) ρ(osuit) (?) (Tybout)²⁷.
- 6.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645624

EDCS 71000785

PHI 337213

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 52.0894

Filippi, A. 2002. Trapani: testimonianze storiche ed archeologiche. *Sicilia Archeologica*. 35: 73-87. At 73 no.15/5

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